
In vivo Toxicity Study and Antifilarial Activity of Four Plants from Nord-Cameroon

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Authors ND, AM, AA and DB designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Authors AM, AA and NTMH managed the analyses of the study. Authors AM and AA managed the literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Aims: The objective of this work was to seek an alternative drug against onchocerciasis based on medicinal plants.

Study Design: Ethanolic extracts of stem barks, leaves and roots of *Detarium microcarpum*, *Guiera senegalensis*, *Trichilia emetica* and *Vitellaria paradoxa* were evaluated *in vitro* against the cattle filarial parasite *Onchocerca ochengi*, a model organism similar to *Onchocerca volvulus*.

Place and Duration of Study: The work took place at the Laboratory of Parasitology of the Institute of Agricultural Research for Development of Ngaoundere between October 2014 and February 2015.

Methodology: Adult worms were incubated in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with antibiotics, and different concentrations of the extracts of the four plants. Mortality was registered after 24, 48

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and 72 h of incubation at 37°C. Ivermectin and M9-DMSO were the positive and negative controls respectively.

Results: All parts of plants showed anthelmintic activities after 72 h of incubation. The Means of LC₅₀ values were determined graphically and varied from 5 to 60 µg/mL after 72 h incubation. The most antifilarial activities were obtained from stem barks and leaves of *D. microcarpum* with LC₅₀ of 5 and 7.9 µg/mL on adult worms respectively, while the least antifilarial activity was obtained from stem barks of *V. paradoxa* with LC₅₀ of 60 µg/mL. These results show that at low concentrations, leaves and stem barks of *D. microcarpum* are effective in killing *O. ochengi* worms. Additionally, *in vivo* toxicity tests using mice showed that the four plants are not toxic.

Conclusion: The findings of the present study support the use of these plants against nematode infections by traditional healers and pastoralists in Cameroon and could represent an alternative anthelmintic for onchocerciasis treatment.

Keywords: Cattle; herbal medicine; river blindness; toxicity; treatment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Onchocerciasis is a disease caused by a parasitic nematode *Onchocerca volvulus*. The disease affects over 36 million people worldwide and is endemic in 20 African countries, in Yemen and parts of Latin America. Eighty-six million people at risk of being infected [1]. It is a human-pathogenic filarial parasite that is transmitted by blackflies of the genus *Simulium damnosum* causing a large spectrum of symptoms and is responsible of blindness [2]. Clinical manifestations are itching and eye lesions which latter lead to visual impairment and blindness [3]. In the human host, the worms live under the skin, where they form nodules at the adult stage [4]. The females of *O. volvulus* produce thousands of microfilariae per day that migrate subcutaneously throughout the human body [5].

The most used chemotherapeutic agent for treating onchocerciasis is ivermectin. This drug is the only existing drug approved for the treatment of onchocerciasis and has been the cornerstone of the Onchocerciasis Control Program (OCP) and later the African Program for Onchocerciasis Control (APOC) [6]. The administration of ivermectin in high doses is not safe [7]. It is microfilaricide, requires more than 15 years of treatment, and causes important side effects which could lead to death in cases of co-endemicity with loasis [7]. These facts with the established resistance developed by *O. volvulus* parasites in some communities in Ghana and in Sudan [8], limit its application [7] and emphasize the importance of searching for new and more effective pharmaceutical drugs to treat the disease.

One of the strategies for developing novel pharmaceutical drugs is to use natural sources such as plants for therapeutics. Isolation of pure compounds leads frequently to the loss of the activity. Owing to the lack of a laboratory host for the human parasite *O. volvulus*, model organisms are often needed. Accordingly, the bovine filarial parasite *Onchocerca ochengi* has been used in some promising antifilarial drug studies [9-13]. The two parasites are evolutionary closely related and are transmitted to their human and bovine host by the same blackfly vector *Simulium damnosum* [14].

Pure compounds isolated from *Cyperus articulatus*, *Craterispermum laurinum*, *Morinda lucida* and *Acacia nilotica* have shown activities with LC₅₀ concentrations ranking from 7.8 µg/ml to 46.8 µg/ml on *O. ochengi* [11-13,15].

Based on information of the regular use by traditional healers, herdsman and pastoralists for the treatment of human and livestock parasites, we have recently carried out a study of the nematocidal activity of a group of plants. The results demonstrated the antifilarial activity of the crude extracts of *Anogeissus leiocarpus*, *Khaya senegalensis*, *Annona senegalensis* and *Euphorbia hirta* with the lowest LC₅₀ value of 30 µg/ml on *O. ochengi* after 72 h [16,17]. Elsewhere, Samje et al. [13] reported IC₁₀₀ value of 250 µg/ml with crude extracts of *Morinda lucida*. Up to present, no crude extract has shown antifilarial activity with LC₅₀ value lower than 5 µg/ml on *O. ochengi* adult.

In the present study, we assessed the *in vitro* anthelmintic effect of four plants namely *Detarium microcarpum*, *Guiera senegalensis*, *Vitellaria paradoxa* and *Trichelia emetica*, with promising nematocidal activities.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Plant Material and Chemicals

The plants were collected in savannas. *Detarium microcarpum*, *Vitellaria paradoxa* and *Trichelia emetica* leaves, stem barks and roots (Table 1) were collected in Wakwa (7°20' North, 13°30' East), Ngaoundéré the Adamaoua region in June 2016. *Guiera senegalensis* parts were collected in Kalfou (10° 16' 56" North, 14° 55' 58" East), Maroua the far-North region in August 2016.

They were identified by a botanist (Dr. Tchopsala) of the Department of Biological Sciences, University of Ngaoundere, Cameroon. A voucher specimen was deposited in the National Herbarium of Yaounde, Cameroon (6499/SRF/cam, 24348/SRF/cam, 20887/SRF/cam and 21818/SRF/cam for *Detarium microcarpum*, *Guiera senegalensis*, *Trichelia emetica* and *Vitellaria paradoxa*,

respectively). Unless stated otherwise, all chemicals were purchased from Sigma (Deisenhofen, Germany).

2.2 Preparation of Plant Extracts

Plant extracts were prepared as previously described [16]. Briefly, 10 g of the powdered material was extracted in 100 ml of ethanol (70% v/v) for 48 h at laboratory temperature (25-30 °C), centrifuged (3,500x g, 10 min) and filtered over filter papers No. 413 (VWR International, Darmstadt, Germany). The clear filtrate was concentrated by a rotary evaporator at a temperature not exceeding 40°C under reduced pressure, lyophilized, and the resulting powder was stored at 4°C. After preparation dried extracts of each plant material were dissolved in growth medium containing salt (M9 medium) (3 g/l KH₂PO₄, 6 g/l Na₂HPO₄, 5 g/l NaCl and 0.25 g/l MgSO₄·7H₂O) and 1% dimethyl sulphoxyde (DMSO)

Table 1. Plants used for *in vitro* for antiparasitic activity

Plants (family)	Parts (organ)	Biological activity and application	Extraction
<i>Detarium microcarpum</i> Guill. and Perr. (Caesalpinaceae)	Leaves, bark, roots	Used for the treatment of constipation, dysentery, conjunctivitis, fever, itch, scabies, and wounds. Treatment of stomach aches, antiviral and antimicrobial activity, moderate antitumor efficiency against cancer cells of the breast. Treatment of anorexia, anemia and sexual erectile dysfunction [18-20]	Ethanol
<i>Guiera senegalensis</i> J. F. Gmel (Combretaceae)	Leaves, bark, roots	Antiprotozoa, nematotoxic, efficient against <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> , active on bacteria, viruses and <i>Trypanosoma brucei</i> [21-22]	Ethanol
<i>Trichelia emetica</i> Vahl (Meliaceae)	Leaves, bark, roots	Is useful as treatment against malaria, cough, gastric ulcer, asthma, cirrhosis, intestinal worms, hemorrhoids, mental illness, epilepsy typhoid fever, hypertension. Activity against poisoning, hepatitis, effect on prostate cancer cells, infections of the skin and mouth infections. Treatment of upset stomach, syphilis and bark is used as a purgative. Leaves serve for healing of wounds [23-26]	Ethanol
<i>Vitellaria paradoxa</i> C.F.Gaertn (Sapotaceae)	Leaves, bark, roots	Was shown effective against headache, for the treatment of sores, diarrhea, skin diseases, activity against salmonellosis, moderate antimalarial activity and antiproliferative effect on cancer cells [27-30].	Ethanol

to a final concentration of 50 mg/ml, centrifuged and aliquoted to determine their activity on *Onchocerca ochengi*.

2.3 Phytochemical Screening of Plant Extracts

Phytochemical content of the extracts with 4 derivatives was determined using the standard known methods. The tannins content was evaluated following the method described by Kumaran et al. [31]. Briefly, 200 µl of the sample were mixed with 35 % Na₂CO₃ (w/v) and 100 µl of Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) reagent was added. The obtained solution was homogenized by vortexing for a minute, incubated for five minutes and the absorbance read at 640 nm. The proportion of tannins was expressed as mg equivalent of gallic acid per gram of dry plant material (mg of GAE/g).

Phenolics content was estimated following the Folin-Ciocalteu principle described by Wolfe et al. [32]. The gallic acid amount is evaluated in a serie of dilution in an aqueous solution by photometric quantification. A titration curve of gallic acid is set during the experiment. Briefly, 50 µl of sample was mixed with 200 µl of 35 % Na₂CO₃, the solution was mixed manually for few second and 250 µl of 1/10 (v/v) FC reagent added. The mixture was homogenized and incubated for 30 minutes at 40°C in dark and absorbance was read at 765 nm with a spectrophotometer (UV-Biowave Cambridge, England). Phenolics content was determined by calculation using a linear equation of the gallic acid titration curve. The content was expressed in mg equivalent of gallic acid per gram of dry plant material (mg of GAE/g).

Quantification of flavonoids was performed according to the method described by Wolfe et al. [32]. 0.1 g of the extract was mixed with 2 ml of an extraction solvent made of 140:50:10 methanol-distilled water-acetic acid, mixed manually and filtered using a Wattman paper. The filtrate was adjusted with a volume of the extraction solvent. 250 µl of the filtrate was taken to a 5 ml tube and top up to the final volume with distilled water: the obtained solution is the analysis solution. Rutin was the standard for titration: 1 ml of analysis solution was mixed with 200 µl of distilled water and 500 µl of aluminium chloride solution (400 mg of CH₃COONa anhydrous and 133 mg of AlCl₃) and the absorbance read at 430 nm. The flavonoids

amount was expressed as mg of rutin per 100 grams of dry plant material.

Saponins were determinate using the methodology of Obadoni and Ochuko [33]. To 0.1 g of the extract, 1 ml of distilled water was added and vigorously shaken for 30 min. The height of moss was measured by a ruler and quantified like following: Saponin (mg) = [(0.432) (height of moss in cm after 5 to 10s) + 0.008] / (weight of sample in gram).

2.4 Sampling and *in vitro* Screening Assay of *O. ochengi* Adults

Nodules removed from the umbilical skin of cattle slaughtered in the local slaughterhouse were brought to the laboratory, washed, drained and sterilized with 10 % povidone iodine (Galentic Pharma, Mumbai/India) for dissection as described by Ndjonka et al. [16]. After extirpation of nodules, *O. ochengi* were extracted, isolated and washed three times with sterile phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). The adult female worms were isolated by digestion of the nodules with collagenase at 37°C. Worms were incubated following the protocol of Borsboom et al. [34]. Briefly, six individuals (1 per 1 ml culture medium/well) were incubated with different concentrations of the plant extracts (0–0.5 mg/ml) in RPMI 1640 supplemented with penicillin/streptomycin (100 U/100 µg/ml). Assays were incubated at 37°C and mortality was determined after 24 h, 48 h and 72 h.

2.5 *In vitro* Assays: Mortality of Worms

Adult worms were washed twice and subsequently transferred into RPMI-1640 medium supplemented with L-glutamine, 100 U/mL penicillin and 100 µg/mL streptomycin and incubated at 37°C in 24-well plates with different concentrations of the tested plant extracts. Worm mortality was checked by observation under the microscope after 24, 48 and 72 h of incubation. After shaking, immotile and fully elongated individuals were considered being dead. All tests were done in three independent duplicate determinations.

The mortality rate was expressed as the percentage of number of dead divided by the number of living swimming worms. LC₅₀ values were determinate (lethal concentration of the extract required to kill 50% of the tested subjects). Results are presented as mean values

± standard error of the mean (SEM). Error bars in bar graphs are SEM.

100 mg of ivermectin (Merck sharp & Co, Rahway/USA) was dissolved in 10% DMSO in distilled water. The drug was diluted with M9 to a final concentration of 2.2 mg/ml (2.5 mM) used for the preparation of the positive control groups and M9-DMSO as negative control. The maximal final concentration of DMSO in the test is 1%.

2.6 Experimentation with Mice

Eight to twelve-week-old BALB/c mice, with an average weight between 20 to 25 g served for the experiments were purchased at LANAVET (Laboratoire National Vétérinaire, Garoua/Cameroon). Animals were housed and maintained at the Veterinary Research Laboratory of the Institute of Agricultural Research for Development, Wakwa Regional Centre, Ngaoundere, Cameroon under ambient temperatures ($25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$) and 12 h light/dark cycle. The access of the animals to drinking water and rodent pellets was unrestricted. Plant extracts, at doses of 1500, 3000 and 5000 mg/kg body weight, respectively, were orally administered separately as suspensions in M9-DMSO to six male and six female mice. After dosing, each mouse was carefully observed at 2, 4, 24 and 48 h intervals for clinical signs, and less frequently twice daily for a continuous period of 14 days. The appearance of toxic symptoms such as behavioural changes, locomotion, convulsions and mortality, were observed and recorded. There is no law yet regulating animal research in Cameroon [13]. All animal-related experimental procedures were approved by the regional delegation of Livestock, Fisheries and Animal Industries (N°075/16/L/RA/DREPIA). The present study was conducted in compliance with the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development guidelines (420) for testing of chemicals [35].

2.7 Statistical Analysis

Results in each experiment are expressed as the mean values with their corresponding standard error of the mean determined using the Graphprism program 5.0 software. Data comparison was made using one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's test.

3. RESULTS

The ethanolic crude extracts from different parts of the tested plants showed an anthelmintic

activity on macrofilariae of *Onchocerca ochengi* at 24, 48 and 72 h of incubation at 37°C with LC_{50} values between 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ to 300 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (Fig. 1).

Different parts of *D. microcarpum*, *G. senegalensis*, *T. emetica*, and *V. paradoxa* ethanolic extracts were tested for antifilarial activity using adults of *O. ochengi*. Ivermectin was the positive control. No mortality was observed during the experimental period of two weeks in the negative control M9-DMSO. Compared to ivermectin (LC_{50} values of 16.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) the ethanolic crude extract of stem bark and leaves of *D. microcarpum* exhibited the lower LC_{50} of 5 and 7.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ ($p < 0.001$) after 72 h on *O. ochengi* respectively (Fig. 1A).

The crude extract of stem barks and leaves of *D. microcarpum*, therefore, caused a higher mortality than the positive control ($p < 0.001$). Fig. 1 shows most of the tested parts of *D. microcarpum* (Fig. 1A), *T. emetica* (Fig. 1B) and roots of *G. senegalensis* (Fig. 1D) exhibit macrofilaricidal activity at LC_{50} below that of the positive control ivermectin at the same exposure time (72 h).

Among the tested plants, crude extracts of the stem barks and leaves of *D. microcarpum* (LC_{50} = 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 7.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ respectively, Fig. 1A) are the most potent extracts against *O. ochengi*. The leaves and roots of *T. emetica* were the second most potent extracts (LC_{50} of 14.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, 12.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ respectively, Fig. 1B). The extract of *G. senegalensis* showed lesser nematotoxicity (LC_{50} = 17.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 12.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ respectively, Fig. 1D). The leaves and stem barks of *V. paradoxa* induced the weakest mortality on *O. ochengi* after 72 h (LC_{50} = 50.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ for both, Fig. 1C).

A phytochemical screening of the tested plant extracts revealed that flavonoids are globally the represented compounds in terms of quantity (Table 2). They are the main component in at least one part of each of the tested plant. From the plant extracts of leaves, stem barks and roots of *D. microcarpum* showed high amounts of the quantified phytochemical constituents (22 to 55 mg/100 g of dry plant product) represented by flavonoids. Nevertheless, the most important amount of compounds namely flavonoids is noticed on the leaves of *G. senegalensis* (174 mg). Elsewhere, saponins are the second leading compounds. They are highly represented in *V. paradoxa* (roots and stem barks), *T. emetic*

Fig. 1. Comparison of LC₅₀ of *Onchocerca ochengi* exposed to different parts of the plants. The calculated LC₅₀ for each time point was represented with standard error of the mean (SEM). (A) *Detarium microcarpum*; (B) *Trichilia emetica*; (C) *Vitellaria paradoxa*; (D). *Guiera senegalensis* (***) $p < 0.001$

(leaves and roots) and *G. senegalensis* (roots and stem barks). Tannins are also represented with weak and very close amounts for all the screened plants (1-2.4 mg/100 g) except for roots of *G. senegalensis*. Phenolics are mostly represented as traces (≤ 0.65 mg/100 g) except for *D. microcarpum* leaves.

Acute toxicity results at doses 1500, 3000 and 5000 mg/kg of the ethanolic crude extracts of *D. microcarpum*, *G. senegalensis* and *V. paradoxa* after 14 days showed no adverse effects and no mortality (Table 3).

The ethanolic crude extract of *T. emetica* showed 33.3% mortality at the dose of 1500 mg/kg and

100% mortality at doses up to 3000 mg/kg (Table 2). At the dose 1000 mg/kg no adverse reactions, no mortality were observed with the four plants tested (results not shown).

4. DISCUSSION

The increasing reliance on a single drug or compound risks the potential emergence of resistance. Plant extract is a cocktail of compounds which act synergically and can improve treatment effectiveness, reduce therapeutic duration and resistance. The present study was undertaken to assess the toxicity of the ethanolic crude extracts of *D. microcarpum*, *G. senegalensis*, *T. emetica*, and *V. paradoxa* on

Table 2. Quantity (mg) of phytochemical compounds (tannins, flavonoids, saponins and phenolics) for each 100 grams of dry leaves, stem barks and roots of *Detarium microcarpum*, *Vitellaria paradoxa*, *Trichilia emetica* and *Guiera senegalensis*

Plant	Part	Tannins (mg GAE)	Flavonoids (mg ER)	Saponins (mg GAE)	Phenolics (mg GAE)
<i>D. microcarpum</i>	Leaves	1.05 ± 0.05	55.00 ± 0.04	10.11 ± 0.58	3.67 ± 0.02
	Roots	1.58 ± 0.01	22.00 ± 0.00	14.43 ± 0.58	0.61 ± 0.03
	Stem barks	1.39 ± 0.01	48.00 ± 0.00	15.87 ± 1.57	0.54 ± 0.01
<i>V. paradoxa</i>	Leaves	2.368 ± 0.00	48.00 ± 0.00	23.07 ± 0.05	0.65 ± 0.02
	Roots	2.02 ± 0.13	12.00 ± 0.08	40.0 ± 5.50	0.45 ± 0.03
	Stem barks	1.49 ± 0.01	1.00 ± 0.00	37.47 ± 1.00	0.52 ± 0.02
<i>T. emetica</i>	Leaves	1.10 ± 0.02	9.00 ± 0.00	20.19 ± 0.58	0.44 ± 0.03
	Roots	1.03 ± 0.03	19.00 ± 0.01	18.75 ± 1.52	0.50 ± 0.01
	Stem barks	1.94 ± 0.01	17.00 ± 0.01	15.87 ± 0.58	0.35 ± 0.20
<i>G. senegalensis</i>	Leaves	2.18 ± 0.01	174 ± 0.02	2.07 ± 1.53	0.55 ± 0.01
	Roots	12.54 ± 0.05	1.02 ± 0.02	33.15 ± 0.58	0.63 ± 0.02
	Stem barks	1.31 ± 0.01	3.00 ± 0.00	40.35 ± 0.53	0.35 ± 0.19

ER: rutin equivalent, GAE: Gallic acid equivalent

Table 3. Percentage (%) mortality of male and female mice 72 h after administration of crude extracts of *Detarium microcarpum*, *Guiera senegalensis*, *Trichilia emetica* and *Vitellaria paradoxa*

Crude extracts	Mortality rate of male and female mice (%)			
	Control	1500 mg/kg	3000 mg/kg	5000 mg/kg
<i>D. microcarpum</i>	-	0	0	0
<i>T. emetica</i>	-	33.3	100	100
<i>V. paradoxa</i>	-	0	0	0
<i>G. senegalensis</i>	-	0	0	0
Ivermectin	0	0	0	0
M9-DMSO	0	-	-	-

the bovine parasitic nematode *O. ochengi*. Our results demonstrate the sensitivity of the nematode to the different parts of the plant extracts.

Recent reports state that *D. microcarpum* is used in the treatment of constipation, dysentery, conjunctivitis, fever, itch, scabies, and wounds as well in the treatment of stomach aches, antimicrobial activity, anorexia and anemia [19-21]. *G. senegalensis* has been reported to have activity on protozoa such as *Plasmodium falciparum* and *Trypanosoma brucei brucei* [22,23]. Studies on *T. emetica* showed that this plant could heal malaria, cough, gastric ulcer, asthma, cirrhosis, intestinal worms, syphilis, infections of the skin and mouth infections. The stem barks were used as a purgative and leaves are used for healing of wounds [24-26,36]. *V. paradoxa* has also been demonstrated having activity against, schistosomiasis, headaches and treatment of sores, diarrhea and skin diseases [37,38]. In a separate study, a variety of bioactive components such as tannins (gallic acid, ellagic

acid, galloylquinic acid and gentisic acid), flavonoids, alkaloids, phenols, tetranorditerpenoids, cis-2-oxokolavenic acid, copalic diterpen acid, coumarin, triterpen, leucoanthocyan, trichilin [39-48] have been isolated from *D. microcarpum*, *G. senegalensis*, *T. emetica* and *V. paradoxa*. Some of these phenolic compounds (gallic acid, ellagic acid and gentisic acid) obtained from other sources have shown strong activity against *O. ochengi* [11]. Remarkably, none of these selected plants except *T. emetica* have been tested on nematodes in general and on the bovine parasitic nematode *O. ochengi* in particular. However, some other plant extracts such as *Annona muricata*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Anogeissus leiocarpus*, *Coriandrum sativum*, *Tagetes minuta*, *Alpinia zerumbet*, *Tragia benthami*, *Piper umbellatum* [9,11,49-53], *Homalium africanum*, *Margaritaria discoidea*, *Alium sativum*, *Tagetes erecta*, *Craterispermum laurinum*, *Morinda lucida* [13,54-56], or *Acacia nilotica* [15] have shown, inhibitory properties against *Onchocerca* worms, gastrointestinal worms and glutathione

S-transferases. All those studies reported are not directly comparable to our results, due to differences in plant materials. Moreover, recent studies using plants mentioned above have also demonstrated that the majority of these plants contain almost the same bioactive compounds namely galloylated proanthocyanidins, polyphenols (gallic acid, ellagic acid, gentisic acid), tannins, flavonoids [11,15,45-48]. Those compounds have been shown to be active against *O. ochengi* and other nematodes. The activity observed on the filarial nematode *O. ochengi* might be attributed to the presence of bioactive compounds such as flavonoids and tannins in *D. microcarpum*, *G. senegalensis*, *T. emetica* and *V. paradoxa* and they might act synergically. Due to the presence of tannins in *D. microcarpum*, *G. senegalensis*, *T. emetica* and *V. paradoxa*, mortality observed might be explained by the activity of tannins. They react directly with surface proteins of the parasite (*O. ochengi*) causing a physiological dysfunction. The parasite mobility and the absorption of nutrients is obstructed leading to its death as observed by Katiki et al. [57]. It has been also demonstrated that tannins also interfere with the production of energy in helminth parasites by uncoupling the oxidative phosphorylation [54]. Another possible anthelmintic effect of tannins is that they can bind to glycoproteins on the cuticle of the parasite and can cause death [56,58]. The properties of this substance might explain possible modes of action of *D. microcarpum*, *G. senegalensis*, *T. emetica* and *V. paradoxa* because the majority of chemical families in these plants are tannins [19]. All these results confirm our findings with the selected four plant extracts; reinforce the existing knowledge and the regular use of the plants by traditional healers for the treatment of helminth infections.

The acute toxicity carried out with all the crude extracts, except with *T. emetica*, at a dose of 5000 mg/kg caused neither behavioural changes nor other signs of toxicity or even death in any of the mice tested during the 14 days observation period. Hence, the LD₅₀ could not be determined. Any test substance showing an LD₅₀ of 1000 mg/kg after oral administration can be considered safe [35]. This result indicates that the compounds under study, when given orally, could be considered relatively safe.

In summary, this work focused on the evaluation of the anthelmintic activity of ethanolic extracts from different parts of *Detarium microcarpum*, *Guiera senegalensis*, *Trichelia emetica* and

Vitellaria paradoxa on nematodes *Onchocerca ochengi* the cattle parasites. It appears from our results that ethanolic extracts of all parts displayed nematocidal effects on adult worms of *Onchocerca ochengi*. We can say that *D. microcarpum*, *G. senegalensis*, *T. emetica* and *V. paradoxa* are important medicinal plants for their broad spectrum of uses.

5. CONCLUSION

These results allowed us to know that different parts of *D. microcarpum*, *T. emetica* and *G. senegalensis* more efficient than or as potent as ivermectin against male adults of *O. ochengi*. Acute toxicity results showed that at single-dose (1500, 3000 and 5000 mg/kg), there is no adverse effects of the ethanolic extract of *D. microcarpum*, *G. senegalensis*, *V. paradoxa*. Nevertheless, additional work could be conducted using *T. emetic* fractions for getting more information about the safety of the active molecule(s). Those findings showed that *D. microcarpum*, *G. senegalensis* could be used in the traditional treatment of onchocerciasis. It would be interesting to extend this work and evaluate the synergistic effect of these three combined plants and a bioguided fractionation for the isolation of their active molecules.

CONSENT

It is not applicable.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

All authors declare that "principles of laboratory animal care" (NIH publication no. 85-23, revised 1985) were followed, as well as specific national laws where applicable. All experiments have been examined and approved by the Animal Ethical Committee of the Ngaoundere Regional Health Authority, Cameroon.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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